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Deliverable D3.1 Interim report on data handling, software development and use cases, including prototype versions of selected software modules.

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Abstract

This report describes progress on developing scientific and societal relevant applications of the DAS fibre technologies. Much of the effort was focussed on developing and implementing methods for analysis of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) data based on open datasets worldwide, although first site-specific observational results are being generated from the Madeira site. Field activities with the purpose of cable calibration have been carried out near the Svalbard and Sines sites and software developments for real-time streaming have been tackled.

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1 Executive Summary

The objectives of WP3 Proof-of-Concept Exploitation are to (1) distribute reduced data sets collected by the SUBMERSE infrastructure as well as higher level data products for a wide range of research communities using established data distribution structures (EPOS-EIDA, Copernicus-Marine); (2) validate the data by carrying out calibration experiments and cross-comparison with permanent installations (oceanographic moorings; land stations); (3) develop methods for exemplary scientific use cases in the geo- and ocean sciences with societal relevance to demonstrate scientific exploitation of the data. (4) Study key local sites offshore Portugal, Madeira, and Svalbard and in Greece; (5) develop and distribute research software tools for DAS and SOP-OTDR data. (6) Engage the relevant research, industrial and societal communities through focused workshops. The first phase of the project work touched upon all objectives, but a particular focus was on objectives 2-3 with data from the already operational sites with continuous DAS acquisition (Madeira and Svalbard), and with SOP (Svalbard). Only limited data sets from these sites have been shared with all project partners due to security and practical concerns. In any case some developments, e.g., the training of machine learning models, rely on large data sets, leading us to also utilise submarine DAS data from other sources, either because they are publicly available or through cooperation.

We note that the different use cases place different demands on the spatial and temporal resolutions required, but also importantly latency, i.e., when researchers or observatory staff can obtain access to the cable. Another important consideration is the precision to which the cable geometry needs to be known. These requirements are presented in a table, but we note that the societally most directly useful applications relating to early warning require generally very low latency of seconds or tens of seconds. If data need an embargo time for security reasons, then procedures need to be set up so that early warning centres obtain immediate access, or pertinent aggregate measurements, e.g., arrival times and amplitudes of phases, and/or down sampled streams.

The calibration task in oceanography focuses on significant wave heights as the most accessible ocean variable causing an imprint on DAS records in shallow water. Here, first wave height models incorporating satellite data were compared to buoy data to be able to make a link to DAS records. An experiment with three ocean bottom seismometers near the Svalbard cable has been recently completed (in September 2024), and data from the ocean bottom instruments will be compared to both DAS and SOP data in the coming months. Seven ocean bottom instruments for calibration of the Sines cable have been recently deployed (September 2024), with recovery planned in March. An ocean bottom current meter is included in this experiment, but the deployment site is beyond the first repeater and thus out of range for DAS, relying on SOP technologies.

For the geoscientific use cases we focus on developing methods and software for the automated analysis of DAS signals for earthquake location. Specifically, we trained an artificial neural network (ANN) to detect and pick P- and S-arrivals in noisy submarine DAS data. Furthermore, we tested a back projection algorithm for earthquake location with an integrated data set involving both conventional land-based seismometers and submarine DAS data, considering a hypothetical scenario of a large offshore earthquake in the Kefalonia transform fault zone in western Greece, recorded with DAS on the Preveza-Crotone cable. Finally, we analysed the records of local and teleseismic earthquakes along the Svalbard cable to assess the capabilities, and report an observation of T-phases from a local earthquake on the Madeira cable; the latter provides unique data of T-phases very close to their generation area and will allow a better understanding of how seafloor topography facilitates conversion of seismic energy in the solid ground to acoustic energy propagating in the water column.

For the oceanographic use cases, the focus was on the shallow portion of the Madeira cable (<~100 m), where both landward and seaward ocean waves could be clearly separated. The effect of a passing storm and tides can be identified as amplitude modulations of multi-day spectrograms. It was even possible to estimate ocean currents based on opposing advection effects for sea- and landward propagating waves, visible as shifts in frequency-wavenumber spectra. Finally, we show an observation of whale vocalizations from two species on the Madeira cable. Vocalisations from a single whale are clearly visible along more than 10 km of cable length.

For the final task, we concentrated on creating the technical readiness for data distribution through the ORFEUS EIDA data nodes. Here, we highlight the development of a plugin for popular open-source earthquake observatory software SeisComp in cooperation with ASN. This plugin allows redistribution of real-time data streamed from an interrogator (currently limited to OptoDAS interrogator) in the standard SeedLink protocol, which is the standard protocol for real-time seismic data transmission. The use of this plugin will make it possible to easily incorporate data from SUBMERSE DAS cables into routine workflows at seismological data centres and earthquake observatories, supporting both the data archival mission and creating societal benefit in the form of improved tsunami warning capability. Furthermore, some sample completed datasets are prepared for archival and redistribution through the EIDA node operated by University of Bergen in Norway and the candidate EIDA node operated by IPMA in Portugal.

2 Introduction

A key goal of WP3 is to enhance the utility and community uptake of the data collected by the SUBMERSE infrastructure by

- 1) development of methods for exemplary scientific use cases; implementation of these methods in open-source software tools.
- 2) distribution of reduced DAS data sets and derived products through community specific portals.
- 3) carrying out show-case studies focussed on the local sites instrumented by SUBMERSE.
- 4) engaging the relevant research and societal communities.

An intermediate additional goal necessary for the success of these other goals is the validation and calibration of the recorded data through dedicated calibration experiments with ocean bottom seismometers and hydrophones, and by comparison with existing instrumentation, i.e. seismic land stations and oceanographic moorings, as well as other information on the targeted variable, e.g., wave-height models in the case of oceanographic applications. The focus of the first part of the project duration is on the method development and calibration experiments. At the time of writing this interim report, two of the SUBMERSE sites (Svalbard and Madeira) are operating DAS interrogators and delivering data, but for security reasons, only limited datasets from these sites of a few days each were made available to project participants (more data are due to be released shortly). Only the site in Svalbard is recording SOP data, with again only very limited SOP data being accessible to WP3. None of the data from these sites have been cleared for public release yet, except selected waveforms from the Svalbard site made available for the DAS monitoring month ([Wüstefeld et al. 2023](#)) and as supplementary datasets to publication. The sites in Sines and Greece are awaiting installation of the DAS and SOP equipment.

In order to be able to progress with the method development in spite of the limited data availability, we obtained other datasets of marine DAS data, either available openly on the PubDAS database ([Spica et al., 2023](#)) or by

arrangement with the data owners. There are hardly any public SOP datasets available yet, so we did not yet tackle the analysis of SOP data.

For sensing using submarine telecom cables, there will be a trade-off between making the best use of the opportunities for science and society and security concerns. To help discussions with stakeholders, WP3 participants have assessed which minimal temporal and spatial sampling at which latency is required to achieve certain goals, e.g., for early warning, hazard analysis, or oceanographic now-casting, see [Table 2.1](#). This table is meant to be used for discussions of managing this trade-off with relevant stakeholders. The interim report gives an overview of the progress (at the end of September 2024) in the various tasks under the background that little data was available for analysis to the WP3 participants.

Table 2.1 Overview of requirements in terms of frequency content, spatial sampling and latency of the different envisaged applications of SUBMERSE DAS data.

Target (research or civil protection)	Sampling Rate	Minimum (Hz)	Minimum Spatial Sampling (m)	Cable geometry info required?	Req. Latency	Products	Comments
Earthquake (EQ) analysis							
Earthquake EEW	1	500	Required (km scale)	<5 s	Triggered waveform; amplitude and travel time picks		
Tsunami Early Warning through detection of triggering EQ	1	500	Required(km scale)	< 1min	Triggered waveform; phase pick with metadata (amp, dom. freq)		
Local EQ monitoring (up to tens of km from cable)	100	30	Required (10s m)	<1 min	Fast information on seismic swarm activities; EQ locations + magnitudes	Triggered waveforms after detection could be a way to reconcile security and scientific needs	
Research: Local EQ analysis for tectonics; EQ	100 (50)	30 (60)	Required relative loc. (Tens m) (10s m)	Weeks to months	Continuous or triggered waveforms / phase picks	<i>PSHA: Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis</i>	
Regional or teleseismic EQ monitoring	20+	150	Required (100 m)	a few min	Triggered waveforms preferred; phase picks with additional		
Structural analysis							
Scholte waves	10	30	relative cable geometry & azimuth	Months	dispersion curves; shallow shear wave structure -> slope stability	Partial data sufficient - no continuous record needed	
Fault identification	50	Ok 20	Only approximate	Months	position of faults along the cable; size of the damage zone	partial data with local/regional earthqu. recordings	
Converted phase imaging (crustal structure)	5	1 km	Only approximate	Months	Interfaces. sediment-basement interface; maybe Moho depth		
Monitoring - velocity changes	10	1 km	Only approximate	Months	Velocity changes with time, purley correlated	Continuous data needed; but gaps could be acceptable	
Volcano monitoring							
<i>NB: Many columns above, esp. "Monitoring velocity changes", and "local EQ monitoring" apply to volcano monitoring; with</i>							
Volcanic tremor detection and location	20	100	Required (100 m)	A few hours	Catalogue of tremor events; cut waveforms		
Oceanography							
Detection of near-shore ocean gravity waves	0.5	10	Cable azimuths & seafloor depths; approximate	<1 hour	Estimates of dominant wave heights and periods	Latency based on eventual use for assimilation in now-	

3 Progress report on calibration experiments

The purpose of the task on calibration is to gain insight into how the fibre-optic measurements that are or will be carried out in the context of SUBMERSE relate to the physical parameters of interest, e.g. ocean wave amplitudes, or the amplitudes of seismic waves. A prerequisite is to have ground truth data available, and where this is not available for direct measurements, a first activity examined the suitability of wave height models assimilating information from remote sensing by comparing to data from sparse ocean buoys, which measure this parameter directly.

For a direct comparison, fibre-optic sensing data from the upcoming installations will be compared to the OBS measurements and the wave-height proxies in the remaining duration of SUBMERSE.

3.1 Oceanographic Use cases: waves calibration approach

For the purpose of testing if the DAS and SOP strain-derived oceanographic variables compare well to the same variables measured directly in the ocean from mature observing platforms, such as moored oceanographic buoys and satellites, these types of platforms need to be operating in very close proximity to the OF cable location and during the same DAS/SOP data acquisition period. At the Madeira site, a wave moored buoy from the Hydrographic Institute of Portugal (Instituto Hidrográfico) was operational during part of the DAS acquisition period, measuring wave parameters that are used to qualitatively compare to DAS strain data that show wave signatures (Section 3.3) at frequencies <0.3 Hz. A qualitative comparison will require the direct derivation of wave parameters from strain records, work that is still in progress (Section 4.1). The change in location of the Greek site, from the Rhodes-Kos cable in the Aegean Sea to the Preveza-Crotone cable in the Ionian Sea, placed the closest operational oceanographic moored buoys at more than 200 km distance (Figure 3.1), hence these buoys cannot be used for calibration or validation purposes. Significant Wave Height (SWH) from near real-time satellite measurements are provided on spatial grids of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ or $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$ km at daily or 3-hourly intervals, however. They could theoretically be used for calibration purposes if interpolated to the cable coordinates; however, this procedure alone might introduce large and difficult-to-quantify uncertainty.

Figure 3.1: Preveza-Crotone cable (black) and bathymetry (in meters) based on the Copernicus Marine Mediterranean Sea Waves Analysis and Forecast Model ([MEDSEA_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_WAV_006_017](#)) bathymetry (adapted from GEBCO bathymetry). The bathymetry is depicted on the model's $1/24^\circ$ resolution grid. The red diamond shows the Pylos buoy location (operated by HCMR, active) and the green diamond shows the E2M3A (operated by OGS, probably inactive).

On the other hand, the Copernicus Marine Service regional wave models provide a good alternative solution to the lack of direct wave measurements for validation/calibration purposes since they also assimilate satellite measurements. In the Atlantic Ocean for the Sines and Madeira sites, the Atlantic-Iberia Biscay Ireland- Wave Analysis and Forecast Product (IBI_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_WAV_005_005, hereafter called the IBI model) covers the geographic area 19°W - 5°E and 26°N – 56°N with a $1/20^\circ$ grid resolution, produces hourly instantaneous fields of wave parameters and assimilates SWH altimeter observations (Toledano et al., 2022) (Figure 3.2 left). In the Mediterranean Sea and for the Preveza site, the Mediterranean Sea Waves Analysis and Forecast Model (MEDSEA_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_WAV_006_017, hereafter called the MED model) covers the domain between 18.125°W 36.2917°E and 30.1875°N 45.9792°N with a $1/24^\circ$ resolution and, as the IBI model, produces hourly wave parameters after assimilating along-track satellite SWH observations (Korres et al., 2023) (Figure 3.2 right).

Figure 3.2: IBI (left) and MED (right) wave forecast CMEMS model domains (from Toledano et al, 2022 left and Korres at al., 2023 right).

The SWH derived from the IBI and MED reanalysis models at the locations closer to the landing points of the cables for the Sines, Madeira and Preveza sites is shown in Figure 3.3 to provide some insight on the waves we are seeking to observe in the DAS/SOP strain data. As expected, the waves in the Atlantic Ocean sites are higher than in the Mediterranean site due to its smaller fetch. Additionally, the Madeira site waves are smaller than the Sines site waves due the positioning of the Madeira cable in the lee of the island.

Figure 3.3: Time series of SWH from the IBI and MED Copernicus Marine Service Reanalysis models for Sines (red), Madeira (green) and Preveza (blue) sites.

Since the CMEMS wave models continuously assimilate satellite observations, are routinely checked against moored buoy observations for biases ([CMEMS-IBI-QUID-005-005](#), [CMEMS-MED-QUID-006-017](#) and appear to yield reasonable results in the areas of SUBMERSE sites (see Fig. 3.3), they will be used in the calibration process for the ocean surface waves use case. Section 3.4 describes in detail the calibration/validation process in the Madeira site using both an oceanographic moored wave buoy and the IBI forecast model.

3.2 Calibration in situ with ocean bottom instruments

3.2.1 Calibration experiment Svalbard site

A 260 km long standard telecom G.652D single mode fibre-optic cable connects Ny-Ålesund and Longyearbyen in the Svalbard region. The initial 66 km of the cable are interrogated from Ny-Ålesund with continuous acquisition of DAS measurement (Rørstadbotnen et al., 2023). The first 4.2 km portion of the cable (between Ny-Ålesund and Kartverket's Geodetic Earth Observatory) is trenched on land and the rest of the subsea portion of the cable is buried into soft sediments at 0–2 m below the seafloor. The OptoDAS interrogator is set to a gauge length of 8.16 m, and a sampling frequency of 625 Hz.

Three K.U.M. Nammu OBS (ocean bottom seismometer) instruments were deployed in Kongsfjorden, a fjord outside Ny Ålesund, Svalbard, on 18 October 2023 (Fig. 3.4). The instruments were placed in a triangular configuration, with a distance of ~1 km, close to the DAS cable (Table 3.1, Fig. 3.5). The triangular configuration was chosen to be able to apply array processing to the data and then compare to the seismic waves recorded on the DAS system. The instruments were prepared prior to deployment in Longyearbyen and then taken with a small vessel for deployment. Time synchronisation and instrument configuration were done prior to dropping the instruments into the sea. The deployment went well and was completed just before sea conditions worsened. The instruments were recovered after ca. 10 months on 28 August 2024. Acoustic distance measurements were carried out to measure the location of the OBS more precisely. The instrument release procedure, where the instrument detaches from an anchor, worked well and all arrived at the surface. They were synchronised to measure the drift of the internal clock, which is required to carry out time correction. The instruments were taken to Longyearbyen for shipment to Bergen.

Figure 3.4: Picture from the deployment of one of the K.U.M. Nammu OBS.

Table 3.1: Overview of OBS locations and deployment period.

Location name	Latitude	Longitude	Water depth (m)	Deployment date	Recovery date
SMSO1	78.9869	11.6397	300	18/10/23	28/08/24
SMSO2	78.9883	11.5925	280	18/10/23	28/08/24
SMSO3	78.9797	11.6083	270	18/10/23	28/08/24

Figure 3.5: Location map of the three OBS in Kongsfjorden given by diamonds. The approximate position of the fibre optical communication cable is given by dashed pink lines. The cable reaches land near a Geodetic Earth Observatory, Ny Ålesund is located about a km further into the fjord.

3.2.2 Calibration experiment Sines cable

This section describes the efforts performed to plan for the deployment of OBS at or close to the EllaLink Sines-Fortaleza telecommunications cable so that ground motion recordings could be compared with DAS and SOP data recorded by SUBMERSE.

Cable coordinates were digitized from hydrographic maps published by the Portuguese Navy for navigation purposes. It is our understanding that these coordinates may not be exact for security reasons. We estimate

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coordinates to be correct to a few hundred meters. Bathymetry in the area was recovered from the EMODNET service.

The deployment location of the OBS had to respect the following two constraints: (1) To avoid danger to the OBS from deep water fishing by trawling, the water depth in the deployment area had to be at least 3000 m; (2) the OBS should be deployed at a distance to the cable at least three times the water depth as a condition by cable operator EllaLink in order to avoid complications due to the possible needs of repairing operations. With this information we defined the deployment restricted area as shown in Figure 3.6, together with the proposed OBS positions. This choice has the consequence that no comparison with DAS data will be able to be accomplished, and it relies on timely activation of SOP interrogation to be successful for the purpose of calibration.

Figure 3.6 Approximate cable routes off Sines digitized from hydrographic maps published by the Portuguese Navy for navigation purposes. The white circles show the exclusion zone where cable operators asked not to place the OBS and the red circles show the planned OBS locations. Bathymetry retrieved from EMODNET service. In the end seven OBS in total could be deployed, see Fig. 3.8.

As was planned from the beginning of the project, the OBS (model Lobster; Fig. 3.7) were requested from the DEPAS German Pool operated by AWI. The group decided to request from the pool 6 OBS with ground motion and hydrophone recording plus one additional OBS with an added current meter, for a total of seven instruments.

The OBS deployment and recovery was performed by the Navy Research Vessel *D. Carlos* from September 30-October 1, 2024. The approximate deployment locations are shown in [Figure 3.8](#). Recovery is planned for February 2025.

Figure 3.7 (left) Lobster OBS by DEPAS. (Right) Ocean bottom seismometers on deck of Portuguese Navy research vessel *D. Carlos*.

Figure 3.8. Final configuration of OBS.

3.2.3 Calibration Madeira cable

The 56 km Geolab at the Madeira site cable is part of 1116 km cable system that connects the island of Madeira at Funchal to Sines. A DAS unit is installed on the GeoLab cable and is shown in [Figure 3.9](#) along with the bathymetry of the area, while the public cable coordinates are shown on [Table 3.2](#)

Figure 3.9: (a) Bathymetry south of Funchal, Madeira, including the approximate position of the cable during the first marine kilometres (red line), positions of buoy (red circle), short period land station FUL (red triangle), and grid points of the Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish-Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast model (IBI; blue crosses) and Global Ocean Physics Reanalysis (ERA5; yellow +). Distances between the cable and the buoy, as well as the closest grid points are shown in combination with the closest channel and the depth at that position of the cable. (b) Depth profile along the cable.

Table 3.2: Public approximate cable coordinates.

Latitude	Longitude
32.6358	-16.9454
32.5715	-16.9528
32.4922	-16.9211
32.4698	-16.8988
32.4326	-16.8470
32.2940	-16.6258

Near the Madeira cable landing point, an oceanographic buoy from the Hydrographic Institute of Portugal, located at -16.9450°E and 32.6223°N (Figure 3.6), was measuring surface wave parameters from 17-04-2018 to 02-02-2023. Part of the buoy's operational measuring period overlapped with the DAS operation period, allowing direct comparisons of wave parameters. The buoy measurements include SWH, sea surface wave mean period, wave period at spectral peak, maximum zero crossing wave height, wave direction and sea surface temperature at hourly temporal resolution.

Although the existence of direct wave measurements at the Madeira site is an opportunity, the small simultaneous DAS/buoy period and the limitation of having one fixed location, justify the additional use of the IBI and MED wave models described at the beginning of Section 3. Comparing the

IBI model's SWH at the point closest to the cable to the buoy SWH time series (Figure 3.10), there is qualitative agreement between the two time-series. Some differences are observed in the maximum wave heights during April and June 2022 where the model shows waves more than 0.5 m higher than the buoy, most likely due to the buoy being closer to the island. In terms of temporal variability, the buoy and model show good agreement which is expected since the model assimilates satellite wave data in near real time. Overall, we conclude that the IBI wave model can be used in place of observations for validation purposes, providing insights into the wave parameter along the length of the cable.

Figure 3.10: Left: SWH time series from the Instituto Hydrographico (PT) Funchal buoy (blue) and the IBI wave model (red). Right: buoy (green star) location, model grid point (black diamond) location and mean SWH from the IBI model (same period as time series on the left panel) for the cable area.

3.2.4 Future calibration steps

For the oceanographic calibration we found that the CMEMS wave forecast model is a useful tool in the exploratory analysis for calibration of ocean surface parameters derived from the DAS/SOP strain data, with its main strength being the spatio-temporal coverage: all along the cable and areas of interest for an extended past period, in real time and in the future. Yet, direct satellite observations should also be considered for calibration purposes.

For the geoscientific calibration we will focus on the analysis of the ocean bottom experiments, e.g., comparing amplitude measurements from the DAS interrogation with those recorded by the OBS, comparing the detection thresholds for the Svalbard array. The array configuration will also allow direct comparisons of the strain recorded by the DAS with the strain inferred by differencing, for wavelengths longer than twice the array dimension. For the Sines site, the focus will be on the comparison of the OBS data with SOP. For the Greek side, once installation has been completed, the focus will be on comparing detectability and amplitudes to nearby land stations.

4 Progress report on geoscientific use cases

One of the main objectives of task 3.2 on the geoscientific use cases is the development of analysis tools that will allow scientists to make best use of the data that will be delivered by the new infrastructure built in SUBMERSE and at further sites following the blueprint of SUBMERSE installations. As only small quantities of data were available to all project participants from the Madeira and Svalbard sites, such developments also relied on submarine DAS data collected at other sites. Whereas these are almost exclusively using dark fibres, ASN have demonstrated with a pilot experiment (on Marseille-Barcelona link cable) that the sensing capability in lit fibres has practically indistinguishable sensing capabilities, so that these methods will be fully applicable to the SUBMERSE pilot sites.

4.1 Local and regional earthquake arrival time picking with machine learning

Submarine Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) data can address the gaps in seismic observation within the ocean, providing additional lead time for earthquake early warnings (Yin et al., 2023). However, manually labelling the

P and S seismic waves in these datasets is both challenging and time-consuming due to the sheer volume of data and the complexity of submarine noise. Unlike terrestrial environments, submarine DAS data is affected by a variety of noise sources, including microseisms, vessel noise, ocean waves, and marine life, which can obscure the seismic signals of interest. To address these challenges, we propose training a DeepLab model specifically on submarine DAS data. We develop tools for the automated analysis of these upcoming data sets as well as other submarine DAS data. Employing DeepLab v3, a cutting-edge deep neural network architecture renowned for its exemplary performance in semantic segmentation, this project aims to develop a specialized machine learning model for the detection of earthquakes and the identification of P and S waves using submarine DAS data. The inherently two-dimensional nature of our input data mandates the adoption of DeepLab v3. Confronted with the distinctive challenges posed by submarine DAS data, which encompass varied oceanic noise environments and a spectrum of operational parameters including cable length, configuration, channel spacing, deployment conditions, and geographic diversity, we have chosen to implement a more expansive model to enhance detection capabilities.

To make our machine learning model applicable to the diverse oceanic environments encountered in the different SUBMERSE sites and also to provide a flexible tool for other sites where continuous DAS recordings will be set up, we have made a concerted effort to gather ocean bottom DAS seismic data from various global locations; this also allowed us to proceed with the work even though the data available to us from the SUBMERSE test sites was limited. Our study leverages DAS data collected from nine submarine fibre optic cables worldwide, encompassing nearly 15 million seismic records (Figure 4.1). This dataset includes some earthquake recordings from the Svalbard and the Madeira sites, but as deep neural networks based on machine learning models generally require large training data sets, the training dataset is dominated by other regions, which had more available data. Additionally, we incorporated land-based DAS seismic records from the Ridgecrest region in California to pre-train our model.

To ensure the quality and accuracy of our labelled data, we adopted a semi-automatic labelling approach. Initially, we used PhaseNet (Zhu et al., 2023) as implemented for the SeisBench platform (Woollam et al., 2022) to perform single-channel labelling, leveraging its efficiency in identifying P and S seismic waves. To enhance the reliability of these labels, we developed an interactive software tool that allows for manual correction of the labelling results. We manually intervened every 5-10 channels depending on the channel spacing, correcting errors that might have arisen due to excessive noise on single component DAS data. The arrival times of the P and S waves for the channels in between were determined through linear interpolation. However, we conducted manual checks to ensure the accuracy of these interpolated times, and if any discrepancies were found, we intervened and corrected them manually. To further enrich the dataset and improve model generalization, we applied data augmentation techniques, introducing noise into these patches to simulate a wider range of real-world conditions. Finally, to prevent potential class imbalance issues during model training, we excluded any waveforms that contained only P or S wave labels, ensuring a more balanced and effective learning process.

This hybrid method enabled us to efficiently and accurately label P and S wave seismic records, ensuring more accurate labelled data for subsequent analysis (Figure 4.2).

As next steps, we are currently preparing a manuscript describing the methodology and assessing the performance in a systematic way. Upon acceptance of the manuscript, we will make available the developed software and weights of the neural network model, which will allow users to apply the picker to their own marine dataset. We will also provide the tools for experts to further refine and adapt the model to the environment most relevant to them by providing the described semi-automatic annotation tool and examples for setting up training workflows. Finally, where licensing permits, we will make available the annotated datasets used by us as a benchmark. Once data are becoming available routinely from SUBMERSE, we will apply our trained machine learning model to these data and set up a workflow for locating events. Furthermore, we will investigate whether variants of the neural network model could operate on selected DAS interrogators directly, with the possibility to export useful scientific data while respecting security concerns for the full data.

Figure 4.1 (a) Locations of all DAS cables used for training or testing of machine learning picker DeepDAS. (b) One of the primary data sources is from the Chilean coastline, featuring three cables: CCN.N, SER.S, and SER.N. The points indicate earthquake locations, with colours representing the time of data collection. (c) Similar to (b) but showing data from the Canary Islands. (d) Similar to (b), but showing data from Kamaishi, Japan.

Figure 4.2 DAS waveform example for ML 4.3 earthquake and small aftershocks recorded on submarine DAS cable in Chile demonstrating the capability of the model to identify multiple earthquakes as well as detect weak seismic events; while not visible in this plot, the shorter blue and red segments actually correspond to plausible arrivals.

4.2 Earthquake location through back-projection methods

The purpose of seismic back-projection within the context of the overall project is to identify and locate seismic events, as well as to analyse their source behaviour. Traditionally, this technique has relied on data from broadband or strong-motion seismic stations surrounding the event. However, in this case, DAS data collected along submarine fibre-optic cables will be utilized. By tracing seismic wave arrivals back to their source, the aim is to determine the precise location of the events and gain insights into the source dynamics, such as rupture velocity and energy distribution, particularly in areas that have been previously unmapped or unstudied using conventional seismic data. This approach is expected to yield several key outcomes: an enhanced understanding of the application of seismic back-projection methods to DAS data, the development of new techniques and adaptations tailored to the unique characteristics of DAS, and the creation of specialized tools to address the specific challenges associated with this data. Additionally, it is anticipated that the integration of DAS data will lead to more accurate event localization and source characterization, ultimately improving seismic monitoring capabilities when compared to traditional methods and data sources.

The adopted methodology is based on the Source-Scanning Algorithm (SSA) developed by [Kao and Shan \(2004\)](#), which is commonly used for local seismic applications (e.g. [Dokht et al., 2022](#)). This method has been successfully applied in numerous cases for event location and source analysis using conventional seismic data. In this sub-task, the SSA will serve as the foundation, and its application with DAS data will be tested. The primary data

source will be submarine fibre-optic cables, which will be analysed both independently and in combination with conventional seismic data from local stations. The algorithm's accuracy in locating seismic events using DAS data will be evaluated. For larger magnitude events, additional seismic source information will be sought, as local back-projection methods have shown potential to reveal more detailed source characteristics when paired with DAS data (Li et al., 2023). Additionally, the SSA2py algorithm (Fountoulakis and Evangelidis, 2024) will be used in conjunction with other packages such as ObsPy and NumPy to form an initial foundation. After initial testing and evaluation, both theSSA and the SSA2py algorithm will be reviewed and updated as necessary.

Two main aspects have been examined so far. The first focuses on the data processing steps required to enhance the quality of the DAS signal, which will ultimately be utilized in the SSA. The second involves assessing the method's analytical capabilities through synthetic tests, evaluating the impact of data channel positioning and the number of channels on improving result resolution.

In the first case, DAS earthquake data from Chile (Rivet et al., 2023) were used, and various preprocessing signal analysis tests were tested. These tests include appropriate filtering, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) assessment, and transformations such as Short-Term Average/Long-Term Average (STA/LTA) and Kurtosis analysis. These preprocessing steps are essential for improving the resolution and quality of SSA results by effectively reducing noise in the data (Fig. 4.3).

In the second case, synthetic tests were conducted using simulated data for the upcoming Crotone-Preveza cable implementation. These tests, performed with and without the inclusion of strong-motion stations in the region, were used to evaluate the resolution and limitations of the SSA (Fig. 1b). This approach assesses the algorithm's ability to accurately locate seismic events within the examined area and to reveal source characteristics in larger events. This test, known as the Array-Response Function (ARF) test, is commonly used in the literature (Fountoulakis and Evangelidis, 2024).

A major challenge encountered so far is the lack of sufficient submarine fibre-optic cable data for comprehensive testing and analysis. As a solution, the project relied on the limited publicly available data, though these often had incomplete or uncertain metadata. Another significant issue has been the high computational cost, driven by the unprecedented data size associated with back-projection implementations using DAS, which presents additional hurdles in processing and analysis.

The next steps during the project include:

- Standardising the pre-processing workflow.
- Locating example seismic events using the SSA, including potential modifications to the algorithm.
- Developing a spin-off tool based on SSA2py (e.g., SSA2DAS).
- Implementing the algorithm in real-time for event location purposes.
- Investigating source characteristics in the case of major seismic events.

Figure 4.3: a) SNR assessment of fibre segments in Chile for the ML 4.0 magnitude seismic event, calculated based on theoretical P- and S-wave arrivals. Appropriate filtering will subsequently be applied to the data to eliminate noise. b) Synthetic tests for a hypothetical strong event along the Kefalonia Transform Fault, in an area where a seismic gap has been identified, using subsampled data from the upcoming installation of a DAS interrogator for the Crotone-Preveza cable.

4.3 Local and teleseismic earthquake observations

4.3.1 Svalbard site

Five days (20–21 July 2022 & 25–27 May 2023) of data (available through National e-Infrastructure for Research Data owned by Sigma2 and operated by Norwegian Research Infrastructure Services) have been made available so far. Several regional earthquakes with magnitudes between 1.9 and 5.5 Mw (Figure 4.4 shows a 2.4 Mw earthquake at UTC 2023-05-27T18:16:13.7) occurred within these days mostly along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge. In addition, a teleseismic earthquake of Mw 7.8 (UTC 2023-02-06T01:17:34.3) that originated at Kahramanmaraş, Türkiye, was detected by the DAS cable, at a distance of 4800 km (Figure 4.5). The dataset for the teleseismic event is obtained from the repository created during the Global DAS Month of February 2023 (Wuestefeld et al., 2023).

The arrival of the S-phase is evident on the submarine section of the cable even without additional processing. However, processing steps are required to make the P visible. The following pre-processing steps are adopted to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The individual waveforms are detrended and tapered. Then the data is decimated in time by a factor of 5, from 625 Hz to 125 Hz with an antialiasing filter. Filtering is applied with different frequency bands. Finally, different wave phases are distinguished by analysing the data in various domains such as time–distance (t–x), time–frequency (t–f), frequency–distance (f–x) and frequency–wavenumber (f–k) domain. Visualization in f–k domain allows identification and separation of coherent seismic signals from oceanic noise in each frequency band based on their characteristic phase velocities ($c = f/k$).

Figure 4.4 Local Mw 2.4 earthquake at UTC 2023-05-27T18:16:13.7. (a) DAS strain data for 5 minutes time window along the initial 66 km of the cable. The waveforms are preprocessed and a bandpass filter of 5 – 10 Hz is applied. Time of occurrence of the earthquake, P- and S-arrivals are marked with red, green and black. (b) Frequency–wavenumber (f–k) spectrum of the raw strain data over the 5 minutes time window plotted in logarithmic frequency. Dotted lines represent the contours of constant phase velocities ($c = f/k$).

Figure 4.5 Teleseismic Mw 7.8 earthquake at UTC 2023-02-06T01:17:34.3 in Türkiye. (a) DAS strain data of 1-hour time window along the initial 50 km of the cable. The waveforms are preprocessed and a bandpass filter of 0.02–2 Hz is applied. Time of occurrence of the earthquake, P- and S-arrivals are marked with red, green and blue. The epicentral distance with respect to the location of the cable is shown in the second y-axis. (b) Frequency–wavenumber (f–k) spectrum of the raw strain data over the 1-hour time window plotted in logarithmic frequency. Dotted lines represent the contours of constant phase velocities ($c = f/k$).

4.3.2 T-phase observation at Madeira GeoLab site

On October 27th, 2023, a small earthquake (M2.7) occurred east of the Desertas Islands, ~40 km away from the end of the GeoLab fibre.

The Desertas Islands are located midway between the epicentre and the fibre (Fig. 4.6). They are a sharp bathymetric rise from an average depth of ~3400 m, and their orientation effectively blocks the path of water reverberations converted from the upgoing wave near the epicentre. For this event, clear P- and S-arrivals are visible, but also multiple branches of T-phases are evident along the entire cable (Fig. 4.6), identified by the lenticular waveform shape, slow onset and high frequency content. The arrival time delay indicates is consistent with a propagation through the upper crust up to the Desertas Islands and then through the water column. The T-arrivals do not share the same amplitude variations as the P- and S-arrivals, further supporting that they are not direct waves. These coherent recording on many different channels present a rare opportunity to study the conversion of seismic waves in the solid Earth to acoustic waves in the water layer at bathymetric features.

Figure 4.6: DAS record from M_L 2.7 earthquake southeast of Madeira; in addition to the P and S waves a much slower wave is visible, with a propagation velocity that indicates propagation in the water layer as a T-phase. The inset shows the bathymetry around Madeira and the Desertas Islands.

5 Progress report on oceanographic use cases

The SUBMERSE project identified a variety of oceanographic use cases to be explored in DAS and SOP OF strain data, ranging from ocean surface waves and bottom currents to cetology. The case of ocean surface waves, in particular surface gravity waves, is the one to be addressed first mainly due to:

- (1) Ocean surface wave characteristics are more easily observed, via satellites and moored buoys, compared to for example ocean bottom current whose observations are very sparse and difficult to acquire. Direct observations of wave characteristics from mature oceanographic platforms are necessary to validate and calibrate the equivalent DAS/SOP derived characteristics.
- (2) For the majority of relevant literature, surface ocean waves appear in more DAS studies (Sladen et al., 2019; Williams et al., 2022; Lindsey et al., 2019; Glover et al, 2024) than ocean currents (Williams et al., 2022; Mata-Flores et al., 2023) or internal gravity waves (Williams et al, 2023).
- (3) In lieu of direct wave oceanographic observations, ocean surface wave models (both forecast and reanalysis) can be used. While the Copernicus Marine Service also provides forecast and reanalysis products for currents, the wave models are routinely calibrated and tested against oceanographic wave

buoys and satellite products. On the contrary, model derived bottom currents are in principle a forced boundary condition to the numerical model solutions at the bottom of the ocean and one should probably refrain from using this information as a ground truth to calibrate against and validate.

5.1 Wave heights, dominant wave period and oceanic currents

5.1.1 Objective and data selection

One aim of the project is to correlate the amplitude and period of the DAS signal with the sea state to serve as a proxy. For that, the data must be calibrated with measurements from adjacent buoys and wave model data. The pressure of oceanic surface gravity waves can be observed on the first marine kilometres of the cable where the seafloor is shallower than ~ 100 m (e.g., Sladen et al., 2019; Williams et al., 2022). Around Madeira, the steep bathymetry only provides a stretch of around 2 km, where the signal is sufficient (Fig. 5.1). The data quality of all channels along those 2 km is high enough to be used for oceanographic observations, while a dataset decimated to 1 Hz with a spatial sampling of 10 m is sufficient.

Figure 5.1: (a) Median power spectral density of every channel in the first 1700 channels for a 30-minute interval at 2023-10-27, 13:59:59. Cable depth is shown in white, the calculated maximum frequencies are shown for a relation of wavelength and water depth of 1 (black line), as well as limits of 0.5 and 2 (grey lines). The peak at ~ 7 s is determined by local conditions representative of the sea state (see also Williams et al., 2019). Red arrows point to sections with low signal-to-noise ratio. (b) Frequency-wavenumber (f-k) spectrum. Theoretical dispersion curves without added currents are shown for the section of the cable subject to ocean waves at channels 450 to 800 (2.30 to 4.09 km), bandpass filtered between 0.04 Hz and 0.35 Hz. The curves are computed for water depths of 20, 50 and 120 m, which covers the extent of the cable on those channels. (c,d) Data after applying a directional f-k filter of 5 km s^{-1} to 50 km s^{-1} , limiting the output to seaward/landward waves. This figure is adapted from Loureiro et al. (submitted to Seismica).

5.1.2 Significant wave height and dominant wave period

As shown by previous experiments using OBS, significant wave height (SWH) variations estimated by a model are comparable to the behaviour of power spectra peaks at different wave periods, and the overall power spectra are comparable to the dominant wave period peaks over the course of 270 days (Corela, 2014), though there are exceptions such that this correlation is more apparent on longer time series. We are currently working with a 1-week dataset from late October/early November 2023. In addition, we have access to data from a buoy close to the southern coast of the island at a water depth of ~135 m and a distance to the cable of less than 1 km.

On the Fourier spectrum, the effects of tides are visible as amplitude frequency shifts with a duration of around 6 h in the range of 16 to 22 Hz (Fig. 5.2). Also, high amplitude anomalies shifting from around 18 to 10 Hz over the span of several days can be observed and attributed to storms. A noticeable decrease in dominant wave period could be observed by the buoy on 29/10/2023, but the relation to the storm still has to be investigated. Over the seven days observed in our experiment so far, no definite trends between the buoy data and the DAS power spectra could be observed. One week of data is not yet sufficient to facilitate a full calibration (see, e.g., Glover et al., 2024, who estimate a longer deployment is required even if more pressure sensors are available in direct proximity to the DAS location).

As reported in section 1.1, we find a good agreement between the buoy data and the ERA5 satellite re-analysis dataset. This allows us to additionally rely on the re-analysis. The next steps will therefore include the calibration using a larger dataset, specifically including times of storms and different sea states, as well as adapting the procedure to data from other sites.

5.1.3 Oceanic current estimation

Two of the main influences on the dispersion curve of DAS data in frequency-wavenumber (f - k) space are oceanic currents (Williams et al., 2019) and wave train incidence angle on the cable (Sladen et al., 2019). However, while a current deflects all branches of the dispersion curve along the k -axis, an oblique incidence angle results in an overall compression of the curve along the k -axis. Therefore, we can probe for these two parameters using a grid-search approach, which is guided by the misfit calculation between the data amplitude in f - k space and theoretical dispersion curves affected by oceanic currents and wave train incidence angles (Fig. 5.3). In addition, it is possible to identify multiple dominant incidence angles, which have been observed in previous studies (Sladen et al., 2019).

We note, however, that there are further influences that can affect the curve, such as a range of different incidence angles and bathymetric complexities. This is particularly observable on the stronger landward side of the curve as a diffuse cloud around 0.2 Hz.

As next steps, this process will be tested on a bigger dataset that shows larger variations in current and incidence angle values. In addition, it will be tested on data from other sites.

Figure 5.2: Example of a power spectrogram over the seven-day period for a channel at 2961 m from the starting point (~600 m from the coast with a seafloor depth of 15.6 m), using 214 samples per Fourier transformation. The Fourier spectrum was calculated with a sample bin size that approximately matches one measurement every hour to be comparable to the hourly buoy data. The top shows the power spectrogram overlaid by the mean wave period as measured by the buoy (black line). The spectrogram also shows anomalies associated with storms (black ellipses) and tides (black dotted rectangular area). The bottom panel shows the temporal variation of the spectral amplitude at 14 s (red line) in comparison with significant wave height data from the buoy.

Figure 5.3: Detection and automated grid search procedure in f-k space for a 30-minute interval on 2023-10-31, 03:02:29 for channels 450 to 550. (a) Detection of signal. Every point represents the best detection in the respective frequency band for the seaward (left) and landward (right) direction. (b) Misfit error surface. Every calculation point is shown by a black dot. The best set of parameters is shown by the red indicator. In this case, it is a water current of 0.15 m/s and an incidence angle of 0°. (c) Combination plot of f-k spectrum, point detection and best solution. The theoretical dispersion curves for a depth of 5 and 13 m are indicated with blue and red lines, the detection limit is indicated by the orange and blue lines. (d) Combination of f-k spectrum and best solution.

5.2 Marine mammals

The detection and analysis of marine mammal vocalizations is one of the objectives for DAS and SOP data recording. The information analysed can contribute to the definition of public policies for species conservation. In this regard we present below a catalogue of the main low frequency vocalizations that are generated by baleen whales in the NE Atlantic. This information allows for a better understanding of the constraints imposed on marine mammal observations by the data recording sampling rate.

The Madeira DAS recordings were visually inspected searching for mammal vocalizations. One example of recorded signals is shown in Fig 5.4. There are two very clear vocalizations, spaced ~50 s with the typical hyperbolic shape, and a faint sequence of signals at ~13 s interval; this spacing between calls indicates fin whale vocalisations, whereas the species associated with the stronger signals need more detailed analysis to be ascertained. The vocalisations at ~10 and ~60 s show a clear multipath effect that could help in the analysis to obtain the slant distance to the cable. The apex of the hyperbola identifies the closest channel to the whale and its curvature is inversely proportional to the distance.

Figure 5.4 Whale vocalisations on the Madeira cable. The red arrow shows fainter signals that are identified as generated by a fin whale (see text).

6 Accessibility and Community use

As a first step to promote community use, the provision of access to reduced DAS, SOP, and SOP-OTDR dataset through the ORFEUS European Integrated Data Archive (EIDA) (<https://orfeus-eu.org/data/eida/>) is a milestone originally planned for month M18. We initially focussed on developing a software, which receives data streamed from OptoDAS interrogator and recasts it on the fly in the standard seismological data protocol for real-time transmissions, seedlink, allowing easy ingestion into the EIDA archives and potentially near real-time manual and automated analysis with small adaptations of standard seismological software and workflows; this development is described in [section 6.1](#). Setting up data access through EIDA has not been possible for Greece and for the Sines site as the monitoring equipment has not yet been installed. Ingestion into the EIDA node of reduced but otherwise continuous data sets relies on the data flow of the raw data into national data centres first. As access is still very limited, we have recently pivoted to setting up setting up EIDA access for those limited datasets already released ([see section 6.2](#)). We look forward to achieving this milestone (initially for DAS datasets) with 2-3 months delay.

6.1 Data access through EIDA

It is planned to provide access to the different data (DAS, SOP and SOP-OTDR) collected at the various SUBMERSE sites through ORFEUS EIDA. While providing complete data through EIDA is beyond the current EIDA capacity due to the large volumes of the fibre optical data, it is feasible to provide a down-sampled version. This has been demonstrated at GFZ with data collected in other projects (e.g. DEEPEN network: <https://doi.org/10.14470/6Q904658>). Furthermore, individual channels can be streamed into the EIDA system in near real-time as described below in Section 6.2. In the next few weeks, we will provide access to a down-sampled version of the Svalbard Global DAS Month data set through the UIB-NORSAR EIDA node, initially restricted to the SUBMERSE partners. Depending on

permissions, it may also be possible to provide access to a single DAS channel from the Svalbard cable through the EIDA node in near real-time.

Real-time data transmission from selected channels of the Madeira cable to the candidate EIDA node at IPMA in Portugal and addition of already released data is also in preparation.

The acquired data, decimated according to national review procedures, will initially be made accessible to users from the archives only after identification and authorization by the data owner. For example, the data might initially be restricted to project participants, and later be opened more widely, but requiring pre-registration. EIDA has already implemented sophisticated AAI tools, which allow access control at channel level, e.g., it would be possible to select a single channel for public distribution and a larger selection of channels requiring pre-registration. The national EIDA nodes in Greece, Portugal and Norway need to clarify what local authorities and cable operators, what rules need to be followed, and any formal agreements needed.

6.2 Real-time streaming to seismology software

The large volume of data from the interrogated fibre, together with the raw data format (generally HDF5), which is not well suited for real-time transmission, limits interoperability with conventional seismic data in earthquake observatories and tsunami early warning centres. An efficient and integrated data acquisition is required especially for the real-time applications envisaged in the project. ASN and GFZ jointly developed the tools and interfaces needed to enable real-time decimated streaming in standard seismological data format miniSEED (http://www.fdsn.org/pdf/SEEDManual_V2.4.pdf) using the SeedLink protocol (<https://www.seiscomp.de/doc/apps/seedlink.html#seedlink>).

SeedLink is an application-level protocol (TCP based) for the real-time transfer of time series data from seismological and environmental applications. A time series is represented as a sequence of packets of variable length and is identified by a station and stream ID. All connections are initiated by the client. During the handshaking phase, the client can subscribe to specific stations and streams. When handshaking is complete, a stream of SeedLink "packets" is sent to the client, consisting of an 8-byte SeedLink header followed by a 512-byte miniSEED record (miniSEED is the standard format for seismological data exchange). A SeedLink plugin is a small program that sends data to the SeedLink server. Data supplied by a plugin can be in the form of miniSEED packets or just raw integer samples with accompanying timing information.

The ASN OptoDAS system uses ZeroMQ, a popular lightweight messaging system, to transmit real-time messages/data. The OptoDAS configuration interface allows users to set up a decimation pipeline to the SeedLink plug-in. The first message contains the measurement parameters formatted as JSON (header). Subsequent messages contain a timestamp followed by raw data bytes. Samples are natively 16-bit integers, so they fit into standard MiniSEED with Steim2 compression.

We developed the `SeisComp_OptoDas` plugin (Fig. 5.5) which converts ZeroMQ messages from the OptoDAS to MiniSEED channels according to the following scheme: network code = DAS

experiment/fibre ID; station code = DAS channel; location code = usually empty (currently using this to track config changes); channel code = HSF (for 100Hz data). In the case any measurement setup is changed, an updated JSON header with the new parameters will be sent to already connected subscribers. The plugin has been made available and documented within the SeisComP package.

The SeisComP OptoDas plugin was tested on three different fibres and acquisition contexts. The data were successfully acquired, passed through SeisComP automatic phase arrival time picking procedure and stored in the GFZ seismological archive. The plugin is ready to be used for the acquisition of the decimated real-time streams from the three regional sites to the three respective national EIDA nodes.

Figure 5.5: Visualisation of real-time processing and data flow to data archives. The data flow is supported by pre-processing in the DAS interrogator software and the SeedLink protocol. The pre-processing of the high-data rate DAS input enables noise suppression, decimation and decomposition to optimize the data stream for seismological workflows and further analysis in SeisComP. The left part of the figure visualising possible pre-processing step has been provided by ASN.

7 Outlook

Looking forward, the installation of DAS interrogators at additional sites are moving forward so that we will soon be able to test and refine the methods researched during the first phase. We will test whether the combination of the described back-projection algorithm with the automatic picking with AI methods can yield benefits, as has been found for conventional seismic stations (<https://github.com/pyrocko/qseek>, Isken et al. (2024) submitted to *Seismica*; <https://github.com/speedshi/MALMI>, Shi et al (2022)).

We will prepare a software release for the software we developed for DAS picking of arrivals and evaluate the possibility to integrate this into the SeisBench platform (Woollam et al. 2022).

Technology in fibre optic sensing is evolving rapidly. For DAS there is the prospect of interrogating beyond the first repeater, thus extending the range into the deeper ocean. Different flavours of SOP based methodologies seem to move in a direction to allow a much higher spatial resolution than was possible at the beginning of the project; some of them can be implemented in existing systems. The SUBMERSE focus on sensing in active telecom systems means by necessity following very high standards with regard to safety in order to maintain the integrity of telecommunications equipment, so it is not clear whether these technological advances can be incorporated during the funding period.

8 Products

8.1 Scientific

Submitted/unreviewed preprints:

- Loureiro, A., Schlaphorst, D., Matias, L., Pereira, A., Corela, C., Gonçalves, S., Caldeira, R. (2024): First DAS observations from the GeoLab fibre in Madeira, Portugal. *Seismica*. Submitted
- Xiao, H., Zhang, S., Moss, R., Zhan, Z., (2024) Using DAS to Image Deepwater Faults and Migrating Whales. *Seismological Research Letters*, Submitted

Conference presentations:

- **Physics 2024 Portuguese Assembly**
L. M. Matias, A. Loureiro, D. Schlaphorst (2024). Aplicação da Fibra Ótica em Cabos Submarinos de Telecomunicações para a Monitorização dos Oceanos e Terra Sólida, (in Portuguese).
- **SSA (Seismological Society of America AGM), 30 April – 3 May 2024 Anchorage, USA**
Tilman, F., Atherton, C., Kvatadze, R., Asero, C., Evangelidis, C., et al., SUBMERSE Project Paves the Way for Continuous Fiber-optic Monitoring in the Oceans with Submarine Telecommunications Cables. Schlaphorst, D., Loureiro, A., Matias, L., Custódio, S., Corela, C., et al., Near-Source T-Wave Observations in the North Atlantic Using Distributed Acoustic Sensing.
- **EGU Galileo Conference "Fibre Optic Sensing in Geosciences" 16-20 June 2024, Catania, Italy :**
Frederik Tilman, Chris Atherton, Carmela Asero, Christos Evangelidis, Marinos Charalampakis, Martin Landrø, Stephane Rondenay, Lars Ottemöller, Vikram Maji, Carlos Corela, Luis Matias, Susana Custódio, David Schlaphorst, Angelo Strollo, Han Xiao, Athanasia Papapostolou, Leonidas Perivoliotis, Jan Petter Morten, Andres Heinloo, and Afonso Loureiro and the SUBMERSE WP3 team (additional members) Towards continuous fibre-optic monitoring in the oceans with submarine telecommunications cables – the SUBMERSE project ;

Deliverable D3.1 Interim report on data handling, software development and use cases, including prototype versions of selected software modules.

Document ID: <Doc Property Keywords>

Han Xiao and Frederik Tilmann DeepDAS: An Earthquake Phase Identification Tool Using Submarine Distributed Acoustic Sensing Data

- **SSA topical meeting “Photonic Seismology: Lighting the Way Forward”, 7-10 October, Vancouver, Canada**
David Schlaphorst (UL): shallow water current sensing;
Han Xiao (GFZ): P and S phase picking with AI image analysis methods

Invited presentations:

- Matias, L.M. (2024). Observing the Earth and the Ocean using submarine telecom cables. Earthsystems Summer School, Aveiro, Portugal.
- Matias, L.M. (2024). Observar a Terra e os Oceanos com cabos submarinos de telecomunicações. Geophysics MsC Summer School (in Portuguese).
- Matias, L.M. (2023). Using submarine cables for natural hazard mitigation and environment monitoring. Encontro Ciência 2023, Ciência e Oceano para além do Horizonte, Aveiro, 5th-7th July.

8.2 Software

The OptoDas plugin has been added to the open source repository for the seedlink server(<https://github.com/SeisComP/seedlink>) as part of the SeisComP (<https://www.seiscomp.de>) suite of programs.

SSA2py(<https://github.com/ifuoutoul/SSA2py>) is an open-source Python project that implements the Source-Scanning Algorithm (SSA) developed by Honn Kao and Shao-Ju Shan (2004). It offers integration with FDSN-compliant web services and is designed to operate on both GPU and CPU multiprocessing architectures. The primary goal of SSA2py is to provide rapid and accurate calculations of the SSA method under near-real-time conditions. Published by Fountoulakis and Evangelidis (2024), SSA2py can serve as foundational code for SSA implementations using DAS data. Future developments may include spin-off codes to incorporate DAS implementation and enhance location capabilities.

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Deliverable D3.1 Interim report on data handling, software development and use cases, including prototype versions of selected software modules.

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